
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LANGUAGE WORLD PICTURES AND NATIONAL-CULTURAL SPECIFICITIES THROUGH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7461300>

Pulatova Malika Botir kizi

Department of English Linguistics

2nd year master student

NUUz.

Scientific adviser: Nazirova Sh.O.

Annotation: *The article discusses the meaning of phraseological units in the study of world culture. The issues of connection between language and culture are covered. The examples also show the reflection of culture based on phraseological units in the Uzbek and English languages.*

Key words: *Linguistics, world picture, language, semantics, national, grammar, culture, human, phraseological units*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada dunyo madaniyatini o'rganishda frazeologik birliklarning ahamiyati haqida fikr yuritilgan. Til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik masalalari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, o'zbek va ingliz tillaridagi frazeologik birliklar asosida madaniyatning aks ettirishi misollar orqali ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tilshunoslik, dunyo tasviri, til, semantika, milliy, grammatika, madaniyat, inson, frazeologik birliklar.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается значение фразеологических единиц в изучении мировой культуры. Освещены вопросы связи языка и культуры. Также на примерах показано отражение культуры на основе фразеологизмов в узбекском и английском языках.*

Ключевые слова: *Лингвистика, картина мира, язык, семантика, национальность, грамматика, культура, человек, фразеологизмы.*

Phraseology is one of the branches of the science of language that studies the etymology, semantics, structure and functioning of phraseological units. In scientific linguistic literature, the term "phraseological unit" is considered in a broad and narrow sense. Some researchers attribute aphorisms, idioms, paremias and catchphrases to phraseological units. In the lexical composition of the language,

phraseological units occupy a significant place, since, they figuratively and accurately convey thought, reflect various aspects of reality.

Phraseologisms for the most part not only denote a certain phenomenon of reality, but also characterize it, give it a certain assessment. In a semantic sense, they correspond to unified concepts, expressing the meaning of objectivity, process, quality, property or method, have grammatical categories determined by morphological forms and syntactic function in a sentence, and reveal patterns in relation to the general system of language, which are manifested in lexical compatibility, stylistic and emotionally expressive coloring of meaning and synonymous connections. Winged words are traditionally viewed as a means of figurative and expressive literary speech. The name of the term goes back to the work of the ancient Greek poet Homer, in whose poems "Iliad" and "The Odyssey" it occurs more than once: He uttered a winged word. We exchanged winged words among themselves quietly. The figurative expression of Homer, which arose from the association of pronouncing a word, as a flight to the ear of a hearer from the mouth of a speaker, has become a term of linguistics. They denote short quotations, figurative expressions, sayings of historical figures, names of mythological and literary characters that have become common nouns, characteristics of historical figures, which have entered our speech from literary sources, etc. Popular sayings, sayings, all kinds of figurative expressions, both literary and everyday origin, can also be attributed to winged words.

Metaphoricity, emotionality, evaluativeness, expressiveness - all these qualities of phraseological units give our speech brightness, imagery and expressiveness. The etymology and semantics of the phraseological fund of the language is directly related to the cultural and historical experience of the people. The phraseology reflects ideas related to work, life and culture of the people.

Phraseologisms are used in everyday speech, in works of art and in journalism. They give the language a special expressiveness, unique originality and often have a bright national character

L.Elmslev identifies three types of dependencies: interdependence (or interdependence), in which one term implies the existence of another and vice versa; one-sided dependencies (or determinations), in which one member assumes the existence of another, but not vice versa; and looser dependencies (or constellations) in which both terms do not presuppose the existence of each other*. The theory of dependencies of L. Elmslev is very close to the theory of relations

N. S. Trubetskoy. ¹The dependencies identified by L. Elmslev, in contrast to the relationships established

N. S. Trubetskoy for phonological analysis, are linguistic abstractions. When selecting them, L. Elmslev does not take into account the significance of those binary formations that are combined by one or another type of dependence.

Dependencies between various components of phraseological units are the most important characteristic of their lexical composition. The lexical composition of phraseological units is heterogeneous. In some phraseological units, all components are constant, i.e. irreplaceable. The irreplaceability of components can be combined with morphological and positional variance. In other phraseological units, substitution of components is possible. In some phraseological units, variance can be combined with the normative replacement of pronouns by variable elements, while in others such a replacement is possible without variance. In all cases, the invariance of the meaning of phraseological units is preserved. Thus, the selected dependences are specific for phraseological units, they reflect the unity of constancy and variability inherent in any phenomenon.

¹ Трубецкой Н.С. Основы фонологии/Пер.с нем.А.А. Холодовича; Под ред. С.Д.Кацнельсона.М.:Аспект пресс,2000-стр182-183

In view of the foregoing, we single out two groups of phraseological dependencies: 1) non-transformational and 2) transformational dependencies. Within each of these groups, in turn, four types of dependencies are distinguished.

Non-transformational dependencies are distinguished according to the principle of the ratio of constant and replaceable components of phraseological units at the same level, i.e. at the level of a phrase or sentence².

Transformational dependencies are singled out according to the same feature, i.e., according to the ratio of constant and replaceable components, with the only difference that these ratios are distinguished both at the level of the phrase and its transform of the sentence and are accompanied by morphological and syntactic changes opinions.

The name of each type of dependence contains the word "constant", meaning: 1) the presence of a constant, irreplaceable significant component (or components) to express this value; 2) the impossibility for any word that is part of a phraseological unit to become a leading member of a series within the framework of a structural-semantic model³.

The selected dependencies distinguish phraseological units about variable combinations of words and compound words and are internal dependencies of the components of phraseological units.

At present time, people more and more often go out into the world, there are intercultural contacts. People have become more proficient in other languages for communication, so it becomes necessary for them to know the cultural component of the language. In this regard, recently, studies of the language in terms of its interaction with culture have become extremely relevant, in connection with which a new special direction has appeared, called cultural linguistics. Cultural linguistics, the development

²Кунин, А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка: Уч. пос. для интов и фак. иностр. яз.– 3-е изд., стереотип./А.В. Кунин. – Дубна: Феникс+, 2005. –стр 237-238.

³ Кунин А.В. Английская фразеология (теоретический курс). Москва.: Высшая школа, 1970. 55 с.

of which began in the early 90s, is today one of the most relevant areas of modern linguistics, whose tasks include the study and description of the relationship and mutual influences of language and culture, language and folk mentality. It has to do with both cultural science and language science. Cultural linguistics studies the national and cultural semantics of linguistic units in order to understand them in their entirety of content and shades, to the extent that is as close as possible to their perception by the speakers of a given language and a given culture. In a word, this is an aspect of linguistics that studies the problem of reflecting national culture in a language. The most complete relationship "language - culture" is reflected in the works of W. von Humboldt, who wrote: "Man predominantly: he lives with objects as the language presents them to him. Each language describes the circle of the people to whom it belongs, the circle from which a person is given to leave only insofar as it enters the circle of another language. "

One of the linguistic units, an important component of which is cultural information, is a phraseological unit. The cultural components of phraseological meaning focus the value-semantic relations that have been established in a given ethnocultural community, and turn out to be a cultural form of the existence of knowledge. As a consequence, we can understand that phraseological units are a very valuable source of knowledge about the culture of the people and are a direct etymological reflection of the national and cultural specifics of a particular linguistic community, and that is why at this time phraseological units are the brightest linguistic unit of expression linguistic culture.

Phraseological units can be studied in cultural linguistics from positions without equivalence, reflection in their structure of mythologemes, historical facts, traditions and customs, imagery, value norms and behavior, etc. Thus, PU (phraseological units) is the most studied culturally-marked unit of the language, since PU reflect the national-cultural specifics of the language, its originality. The phraseological unit captures the rich historical experience of the people, it reflects ideas related to work, life and culture of people. The study of

phraseology is a necessary link in the assimilation of the language, in improving the culture of speech. The correct and appropriate use of phraseological units gives speech a unique originality, special expressiveness, accuracy, imagery. That is why, the task of our research includes the analysis of phraseological units from the point of view of their national and cultural specifics⁴. As the analysis of our material has shown, phraseological units with a component of a body part are also of particular interest for linguoculturological studies. This group of phraseological units is a clear example of the action of not only linguistic, but also extralinguistic factors in the language. It is during their analysis that it is possible to identify both common features inherent in the human community, regardless of linguistic affiliation, and specific features due to purely extralinguistic factors. The main element of any comparison is the identification of identical (integral) and distinctive (differential) features of the compared phenomena. The postulate of identities and differences in language, formed by F. de Saussure, underlies a number of the most important methods of language analysis - opposing, field, transformational, component, etc. "As a result of formal and semantic comparison and opposition, members of language systems of any scale - grammatical paradigms, antonymic pairs, etc., and vice versa, an exhaustive description of any individual linguistic phenomenon presupposes the allocation of a set of various aspects, forms, meanings and other differences in it, and on the other hand, the inclusion of this phenomenon in various communities on the basis of some identities - formal, semantic, functional, etc. "⁵ Comparison of specific phraseological units provided researchers with material for generalizations in various directions: in translation theory, in phraseography theory, in comparative typological studies.

Phraseological units with components of a body part can express the following conceptual features in two different languages:

⁴ Кунин А.В. Английская фразеология (теоретический курс). Москва.: Высшая школа, 1970. 67 с.

⁵ de Saussure, F. *Cours de linguistique generale*. Paris: Payot. 1995. P 76.

I. The psychological state of a person. This group refers to the description of feelings, emotional, psychological states of a person:

a) fear, fright:

Eng.: *white at the lips; have one's heart in one's mouth;*

Uzb.: *yuzidan rangi uchgan, yuzi oqarib ketdi;*

b) anger and rage:

Eng: give smb a black eye, black in the face; blue in the face; catch by the throat

; Uzb: *bo'g'zidan olmoq, yer yuzidan yo'qotmoq;*

c) aggressiveness, irritation, resentment:

Eng: red in the face; fed to the teeth; up to the eye; to become red in the face; black (blue) in the face; fly in the face;

Uzb: *yuziga sapchimoq;*

d) state of amazement, surprise:

Eng: to be blue in the face;

Uzb: *ko'zi chiqib ketay dedi, og'zi ochilob qoldi;*

e) embarrassment, shyness, shyness:

Eng: to redden to the roots of one's hair;

Uzb: *yuzi qizarib ketdi;*

f) human mood:

Eng: to get out of bed on the wrong foot;

Uzb.: *o'rnidan chap yoni bilan turmoq;*

g) sentimentality:

Eng: have smth. at heart; tender heart; it makes the heart bleed;

Uzb: *ko'ngliga olmoq; bag'ri qon bo'lmoq;*

h) value attitude towards someone:

Eng: the apple of one's eyes;

In world linguistics, research has been conducted in a number of areas, such as the interpretation of figuratively motivated phraseological units, their form and semantic relationship, the study of linguocultural tools and comparative analysis of the use of phraseological units in speech, their lexical-semantic and grammatical classification. being carried out. Comparative analysis of PU is the most optimal means of identifying the

national-cultural specifics of PU Phraseological units present in the language can be divided into the following groups: phraseological units related to place names, phraseological units expressing the human state of mind, phraseological units expressing the human state of mind, and so on. One of the important tasks facing linguists is the problem of structural morphological and lexical-semantic formation of phraseological units of phraseological units that express the mental state of man in English and Uzbek.

CONCLUSION

Today in linguistics there are several different approaches to identifying the national-cultural component of phraseological units: 1) Linguistic and cultural direction, concentrated on the background knowledge of native speakers and on non-equivalent vocabulary; 2) A contrasting approach, the purpose of which is to identify not the general, as in the classical comparative method, but to identify the differences that make up the national-cultural originality of the phraseological equivalents of the compared languages; 3) The linguoculturological approach to the study of phraseology directs the researcher to the study of the ratio of phraseological units and signs in culture and actualizes the meaning of the system of standards, stereotypes, symbols, etc. to describe the cultural and national specifics of the phraseological system.

REFERENCES

1. Трубецкой Н.С. Основы фонологии/Пер.с нем.А.А. Холодовича; Под ред. С.Д.Кацнельсона.М.:Аспект пресс,2000-стр182-183
2. Кунин, А.В. Курс фразеологии современного английского языка: Уч. пос. для интов и фак. иностр. яз.– 3-е изд., стереотип./А.В. Кунин. – Дубна: Феникс+, 2005. –стр 237-238
3. Кунин А.В. Английская фразеология (теоретический курс). Москва.: Высшая школа, 1970. 55 с.
4. Кунин А.В. Английская фразеология (теоретический курс). Москва.: Высшая школа, 1970. 67 с.
5. de Saussure, F. *Cours de linguistique generale*. Paris: Payot. 1995. P 76.
6. Abduraimova Anora Norbotaevna Linguaculturologic aspects of phraseological units with body parts in english, russian and uzbek languages emergent: JOURNAL

OF EDUCATIONAL DISCOVERIES AND LIFELONG LEARNING (EJEDL)
ISSN:2776-0995 Volume 2, Issue 5, May ,2021 p227,228,230

7. Khodjaeva, N. (2019). SEMANTICS OF KINSHIP TERMS AS A FORM OF ADDRESS IN UZBEK TRANSLATIONS OF PREMCHAND. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (8), 107-110.

8. KHODJAEVA, N. B. (2021). PREMCHAND'S VARDAAN IN UZBEKISTAN: TRANSLATION ISSUES OF SOME CULTURAL SPECIFIC WORDS. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (12), 374-377.

9. KHODJAEVA, N. The Development of Indian Literature in Uzbekistan: Historiography of Translation. *History of Translation in India*, 431.

10. Ходжаева, Н., & Губаева, Х. (2020). ISSUES ON TRANSLATION OF CHARACTER SPEECH (ON THE EXAMPLE OF KOREAN-UZBEK LITERATURE). *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 3(4).

11. Khodjayeva, N. (2021). The issues of stylistics on translation of historical costumes. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 534-543.